

Diesel Particulate Filter Pressure Drop

Sandeep Mahajan¹, Kedar Kolhapure²

¹Sandeep Mahajan, Sandeep.eng02@gmail.com

²Kedar Kolhapure, kedarkolhapure@diems.com

Author Correspondence: Department of mechanical Engineering, Deogiri Institute Of Engineering And Management Studies Chh. Sambhajinagar.

Abstract

Particulate matter (PM) emitted from diesel vehicles has serious threats to the global climate, environment, and human health. Diesel particulate filters (DPFs) are currently the only effective after-treatment technology for reducing PM emissions, making it crucial to evaluate their filtration and pressure drop performance using numerical methods. This study developed and validated a lumped model based on spherical packed bed theory and Darcy's law to describe the dynamic PM filtration process in DPFs. The model accurately predicts real-time characteristics such as wall porosity, soot load, and pressure drop. Additionally, it examines the influence of channel characteristics, monolithic size, and exhaust conditions on filtration and pressure drop performance. Results indicate that increasing cell density, wall thickness, DPF length, and diameter enhances filtration efficiency, while higher DPF inlet temperatures and exhaust mass flow rates negatively impact performance. Moreover, wall thickness, DPF diameter, and exhaust flow rate significantly affect total pressure drop. These findings enhance dynamic performance prediction in PM filtration and provide a theoretical foundation for optimizing DPF structures.

1. Introduction

Mobile source emissions have severe impacts on the global climate, environment, and human health, with automobiles being the main contributors. Diesel vehicles, in particular, are responsible for over 80% of nitrogen oxide (NO_x) emissions and 90% of particulate matter (PM) emissions from mobile sources. PM consists of solid particles and carbides produced as by-products of diesel combustion, while NO_x forms through the reaction of oxygen and nitrogen at high combustion temperatures [1]. The small particle size and high inhalability of PM from diesel exhaust allow it to penetrate deeply into the lungs, posing serious health risks [2]. Meanwhile, NO_x emissions significantly contribute to environmental issues such as photochemical smog and acid rain. [3]

In recent decades, significant progress has been made to mitigate PM and NO_x emissions from diesel vehicles, driven by increasingly stringent emission regulations [4-5]. Advances have been made in areas like alternative fuels, fuel additives, engine optimization, combustion strategies, and exhaust aftertreatment technologies. Diesel particulate filters (DPFs) have emerged as the most effective aftertreatment device for reducing PM emissions. These dense filters capture nano- to micron-sized particles, greatly reducing both the mass and number of particles in the exhaust [6-7]. Wall-flow honeycomb ceramic DPFs consist of parallel channels connected by porous substrate walls, with alternating ends of the channels blocked. As exhaust flows through these channels, PM is trapped and deposited on the porous walls. Over time, however, the filters accumulate particles and may develop an ash layer that cannot be removed by regeneration, leading to excessive particle build up [11]. This build up can

increase exhaust backpressure, resulting in engine performance degradation air intake and exhaust efficiency, compromising combustion, and resulting in substantial decreases in power, reliability, and even difficulties in engine starting [12]. As a result, periodic DPF regeneration is required to eliminate the accumulated soot. Precisely determining the timing of this regeneration is vital for ensuring safety and efficiency. Current methods for determining regeneration timing include those based on exhaust back pressure, mileage, fuel consumption, and driving duration. However, the soot accumulation process is complex, with various factors influencing how soot is deposited in the DPF. Accurately assessing the detailed distribution of soot within the filter walls is difficult without advanced testing and characterization tools. Furthermore, due to the DPF's unique honeycomb porous structure, real-time soot loading is challenging to measure directly using sensors or other equipment, so most current methods estimate soot loading indirectly. Understanding the collection mechanism, distinguishing filtration stages, and accurately predicting pressure drop and soot loading are critical for successful DPF operation, particularly regarding regeneration control and diagnostics [13]. Therefore, accurately simulating DPF filtration and pressure drop performance using numerical methods is essential [14]. The process of PM (particulate matter) loading in DPFs has been a key research focus, with many studies examining how exhaust particles percolate and deposit inside the filters. The spherical packed bed filtration theory, which assumes the filter medium consists of spherical collection units, is widely used for wall-flow honeycomb ceramic DPFs [15-16]. As illustrated in Figure, the centre of each spherical collection unit represents the solid portion, while the surrounding area corresponds to the porous part of the wall [17].

Fig. Soot deposition evolution around the spherical packed bed unit collector.

When exhaust PM passes through the filters, it is first collected inside the porous medium wall, which is referred to as the deep-bed filtration stage [18]. Once the amount of soot deposited on the wall surface reaches a certain threshold, the PM starts accumulating as a particle layer on the filter inlet channels' surface. This stage is known as cake filtration, during which subsequent inflowing particles are difficult to enter the wall [19]. It is worth noting that between the deep-bed filtration stage and the cake filtration stage, there is a transitional filtration stage. In this stage, it is generally believed that soot grows in a dendritic or hill-like manner, developing from the interior of the wall to the surface of the inlet channel, until a uniform cake layer is formed. The particle filtration efficiency is directly influenced by various factors, including the average pore size, porosity, wall thickness, and substrate material of the porous medium [20]. The accumulation of soot and ash in the substrate wall results in a substantial increase in filtration efficiency throughout the deep-bed filtration stage. In addition, the cake-layer filtration stage is characterized by a progressive increase in cake layer thickness and a gradually flattened filtration efficiency [21]. Mohammed et al. [22] considered the influence of soot deposited on the surface of the porous medium on the formation of the cake layer, and the cake filtration efficiency can be determined based on empirical data. Zhang et al. [23] proposed the wall saturation index to control the process of soot deposition during deep-bed filtration and distinguished the transitional stage and the cake filtration stage based on the critical porosity value and the formation of the cake layer. Gong et al. [24] established a heterogeneous multiscale filtration (HMF) model and applied it to the simulation of soot deposition in DPFs. The model incorporated the consideration of the probability

density function (PDF) of DPF pore size distribution based on the packed-bed theory [25,26]. Qi et al. [27] established a quasi-two dimensional model based on the assumption of soot fragmentation. They investigated the influence of passive regeneration on the filtration efficiency of DPF and proposed an extended DPF filtration model based on particle morphology characteristics to modify the classical filtration model. Zhang et al. [28] proposed a method to improve the accuracy of transient DPF simulation model by optimizing DPF fitting parameters using the Fletcher-Reeves conjugate gradient method and conducting verification under transient conditions. Zhou et al. [29] studied the influence of exhaust temperature and porosity on DPF filtration efficiency and explored its optimization windows. Chen et al. [30] utilized machine learning methods to optimize DPF performance during the soot loading process for multiple objectives, including high initial filtration efficiency and low pressure drop. Li et al. [31] built a prediction model based on a one-dimension convolutional neural network (1D-CNN) method and utilized the optimal feature data set constructed by temperature difference, pressure difference, and exhaust mass flow to achieve accurate recognition of DPF carbon load. Other researchers also have contributed to enhancing the accuracy of DPF soot loading prediction and improving DPF performance.

The PM loading leads to the blockage of filter pores, resulting in decreased permeability. The DPF pressure drop is often used as a measure of PM load to assist in the design of effective DPF control strategies, thereby preventing excessive fuelling and incomplete regeneration [31,32]. Significant contributions have been made to the development of classical DPF pressure drop models [31,32]. In recent years, researchers have made notable improvements and extensions to this work. Singh et al. [33] conducted experimental tests on different substrate materials, such as SiC, aluminium titanate, and acicular mullite, under various levels of PM loading. They also investigated the impact of catalytic coating on PM oxidation. Zhang et al. [34] developed a one-dimensional semi-open DPF pressure drop model and validated it using computational fluid dynamics (CFD) tools. Wang et al. [35] proposed a data-driven model that maps pressure signals to soot concentrations for the transient prediction of raw PM emissions. Li et al. [36] introduced an improved one-dimensional numerical model and derived formulas for inlet and outlet pressure drops to enhance the accuracy of pressure drop prediction. Chen et al. [37] proposed a combined approach using filter layers (FLs) and a new algorithm based on fast Fourier transform (FFT) to reduce transient pressure signal hysteresis and fluctuations in exhaust temperature and flow during the filtration process. Zhao et al. [38] proposed a pressure drop model that accounted for slip flow and shape correction, leading to improved prediction accuracy. Huang et al. [39] developed a three-dimensional simulation and mathematical model for rotational diesel particle filters (RDPF) and explored the impact of flow factors, such as particle volume fraction, flow velocity, etc., on flow field uniformity.

It is clear that the prediction of DPF pressure drop remains a prominent area of interest for researchers. However, it is important to note that the deposition in DPF is a dynamic and continuous process, and the microscopic physical properties of the filters change as soot accumulation increases. Current research on the real-time description of the DPF soot-loading regime, especially the dynamic filtration characteristics during the transitional stage, still requires further discussion. Additionally, the relationship between particle deposition and pressure drop should be comprehensively investigated. Considering collection mechanisms, including Brownian diffusion, interception, and inertial collision, this study develops a lumped filtration-pressure drop model that redefines the transition of the filtration phases to better describe the dynamic process of PM loading in the DPF. The established model can predict real-time properties such as wall permeability, porosity, collected soot mass, cake layer thickness, and pressure drop composition. The simulation results were validated via a diesel test rig. Furthermore, with the help of the lumped model, the influence of channel characteristics, monolithic size, and exhaust conditions on the filtration efficiency and pressure drop of the DPF is investigated, providing a reference for the structural optimization of DPF.

2. Pressure drop model

Figure shows the exhaust flow and pressure drop components in a single DPF channel. It can be observed that the exhaust flow is impeded by the DPF inlet and outlet channels, cake layer, and wall layer. Consequently, both deep-bed filtration and cake filtration contribute to the rise in DPF pressure drop. By examining the components of the total pressure drop and establishing their correlation with soot deposition, it is viable to accurately estimate the pressure drop and soot loading level in real-time, thereby enabling the quantitative evaluation. Generally, if all DPF channels have the same structure, the investigation of pressure drop can be simplified to considering a single channel.

Fig. Schematic diagram of exhaust gas flow and pressure drop components in a single wall-flow DPF channel.

Demonstrates the key components of DPF pressure drop, which are as follows:

- i. Inertial contribution: This occurs due to the local contraction and expansion of the exhaust flow at the inlet and outlet of the channel.
- ii. Frictional contribution: This is caused by the axial movement of gas along the channel.
- iii. Darcy's contribution: This is a result of the flow through the cake and the porous wall layer.

$$\Delta P_{DPF} = \underbrace{\Delta P_{contr} + \Delta P_{expan}}_{inertial} + \underbrace{\Delta P_{channel,in} + \Delta P_{channel,out}}_{friction} + \underbrace{\Delta P_{cake} + \Delta P_{ash} + \Delta P_{wall}}_{Darcy} \quad (1)$$

The pressure drop term accounts for inertial losses due to the contraction and expansion of exhaust flow are dependent on gas density and velocity. They are given by

$$\Delta P_{contr} = \frac{1}{2} \xi_{contr} \rho_g u_{in}^2$$

$$\Delta P_{expan} = \frac{1}{2} \xi_{expan} \rho_g u_{out}^2 \quad (2)$$

$$\Delta P_{expan} = \frac{1}{2} \xi_{expan} \rho_g u_{out}^2 \quad (3)$$

Where ζ_{contr} and ζ_{expan} denote the dimensionless contraction/expansion inertial loss coefficients, which has a typical range from 0.2 to 1.2. The specific value depends on the filter's fractional open cross-sectional flow area and the Reynolds number.

The channel velocity can be expressed using exhaust volume flow rate and channel geometry. The exhaust through a DPF channel is subjected to friction. Besides, the increase in cake layer thickness leads to a decrease in the effective filtration width of the channel, thereby affecting the pressure drop contribution of friction. This pressure drop component in a channel with a square cross-section can be mathematically expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta P_{fract} &= \Delta P_{channel,in} + \Delta P_{channel,out} \\ &= \frac{F_w \mu}{3} \left(\frac{u_{in} L_{in}}{(\alpha - 2(\omega_c + \omega_a))^2} + \frac{u_{out} L_{out}}{\alpha^2} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

On the other hand, it is important to mention that during the filtration process, only the inlet channel is involved, and no PM collecting is expected to take place in the outlet channel. The characteristic filtration velocity of the exhaust in the porous medium is determined by the flow rate and the effective size of the inlet channel.

The Darcy's law of percolation, essential for understanding flow through porous media, is represented. Additionally, demonstrate the application of Darcy's law specifically to the porous wall of the DPF. The Forchheimer term, i.e., the second term to the right becomes influential at high flow rates. However, it has been proved that the Forchheimer term for the DPF substrate wall can be considered negligible [27, 58]. Hence, its impact on the total pressure drop is disregarded in this study.

In practical diesel engine operation, the time taken for exhaust gas to pass through the DPF porous medium is much less than 1 ms, and thus the volume flow rate and filtration velocity of exhaust flowing through cake and wall layer at any time can be considered the same. Hence, the Darcy's pressure drop can be calculated by considering the Darcy terms of the soot layer, ash layer, and wall layer on a single channel scale as follows:

Therefore, the DPF pressure drop during PM filtration (including deep-bed, transitional and cake filtration phase) can be calculated by

Where the overall equivalent permeability of the n-layer porous wall is given by

As solving for the pressure drop in the DPF requires knowledge of various factors such as flow characteristics, filter geometry and soot load properties. Among them, it is particularly important to calculate the permeability of each porous medium layer. In order to identify the wall permeability, consider a clean state where the thickness of the soot and ash layer is assumed to be zero.

The relationship between the clean state DPF pressure drop and the exhaust volume flow is clearly a quadratic function. For convenience, let

The coefficients a and b here are fixed values that are determined by the characteristics of the filter and the porous medium. The only variable in the equation is the initial wall permeability kw_0 . To obtain kw_0 , it is necessary to conduct clean-state DPF pressure drop measuring tests at various exhaust flow rates.. Then the calibrated kw_0 serves as a baseline for further assessing the wall permeability during the soot loading phase.

3. Experimental setup

The tests were conducted via an engine test bench, which is depicted in Fig. The employed engine was a 6-cylinder turbocharged and intercooled heavy-duty diesel engine that compliant with the Indian BS6 regulations. A DOC + DPF + SCR aftertreatment system was adopted. To measure the concentration of particulate mass and particulate number (PN) upstream and downstream of the DPF, a micro soot sensor AVL MSS-483 and a particle counter AVL 489 were employed. Additionally, temperature sensors and pressure difference sensors were installed to monitor the inlet temperature and pressure drop across the DPF, respectively. To weigh the DPF, a high-precision electronic balance was utilized. Detailed information of the engine, aftertreatment, test device and fuel are shown in Table 2, Table 3 and Table 4 , respectively

In order to obtain the necessary input and output quantities for parameter identification, experiments were conducted. The input quantities included exhaust temperature, exhaust mass flow rate, DPF inlet PM concentration and PN concentration. These variables are closely related to engine operating conditions and have a significant impact on the filtration performance of the DPF which is reflected in the output quantities, including pressure drop and collected soot mass, etc. Therefore, it is important to select appropriate operating conditions for bench tests. For this study, 15 different engine operating points were chosen, consisting of 3 speeds (1000 rpm, 1800 rpm and 2400rpm) and 5 torques (50Nm, 100 Nm, 200 Nm, 300 Nm, 350 Nm). For each condition, the experimental data was sampled every 30 min. The stable value within this time interval was calculated. A total of 3 measurements were taken and the average value was obtained. The selected operating points covered the low to medium load regions of heavy-duty diesel engines while avoiding the high load region. There are several reasons behind this selection. Firstly, increasing the load will lead to higher fuel injection quantities, resulting in higher engine-out PM emissions. Excessive PM trapped within the DPF wall can quickly deteriorate its clean state, which makes the calibration of kw_0 difficult. Secondly, excessively high loads can generate a large amount of heat during fuel combustion, leading to significantly increased exhaust temperature. This high temperature, combined with the presence of NO₂ in the exhaust, can trigger thermal-type passive regeneration reactions that consume PM significantly, which can interfere with the estimation of PM loading levels as well as the calibration of DPF wall parameters. Therefore, the exhaust temperature of every operating point in this study is below 320 °C.

Fig. Schematic diagram of the experimental system.

Table 1

Specifications of the engine.

Parameter	Specification/value
Number of cylinders	4
Fuel injection system	Common rail
Suction type	Turbocharged intercooler
Bore (mm)	90.9
Stroke (mm)	100
Displacement (L)	7.7
Rated power (kW)	250 @ 3200 rpm
Maximum torque (Nm)	350 @ 1400–1400 rpm
.Idle speed (rpm)	850

Table 2

Specifications of the aftertreatment system.

Parameter	DOC	DPF	SCR
Material	Cordierite	SiC	Cordierite
Catalyst	Pt, Pd	–	Cu-SSZ-13
Diameter × length (mmXmm)	250	Φ 250	Φ250
Cell density (#/inch ²)	400	300	400
Wall thickness (mm)	0.10	0.18	0.10
Volume (L)	3.7	3.9	4.9

Table 3

Information of the test equipment.

Equipment	Specification	Manufacturer
Electric dynamometer	AVL DynoDur 330	AVL
Gas emission analyser	AVL AMA 160	AVL
Fuel consumption meter	AVL 735S/753C	AVL
Particulate counter	AVL 489	AVL
Micro soot sensor	AVL 483	AVL
Electronic weighing scale	MT-R	Phonix

Table 4

Properties of the pure diesel.

Fuel parameter	Reference	Result	Analytic method
Density, 20°C (kg/m ³)	810 ~ 845	842.4	GB/T 1884–2004
Sulfur (mg/kg)	<10	2.8	SH/T 0689 2000
Acidity (mg/100 mL)	<7	3.54	GB/T 258–2016
Cold filter plugging point (°C)<4		7	NB/SH/T 0248–2019
Flash point (°C)	>60	75.0	GB/T 261–2021
Cetane index	>46	51.6	SH/T 0694–2007
Distillation, 50 % (°C)	<300	281.3	GB/T 6536–2010
Distillation, 90 % (°C)	<355	329.4	GB/T 6536–2010
Distillation, 95 % (°C)	<365	340.2	GB/T 6536–2010

In addition, after completing the measurement of one operating condition, an activity regeneration activity was performed and maintained for 10 min to completely remove soot particles from the DPF. Subsequently, a scavenging process was followed until the exhaust temperature cooled down to the level of idle speed. By following these procedures, the necessary data for parameter calibration could be obtained accurately and reliably, with interference from the airflow and the residual PM eliminated.

4. Results and discussion

5.1 Model verification

4.1.1. Prediction of PM loading rate at DPF inlet

By adopting the particle effective density in **Eqs** the inlet PM concentration of DPF (with an average particle diameter of 75 nm), as an important input for the filtration model, can be calculated. Fig. indicates a good agreement between the predicted inlet PM concentration and the experimental value. This prediction can be utilized to estimate the flow rate of PM under different operating conditions. The average error in the medium–high speed range is 2.2 %. However, in low speed and high load conditions, the accuracy of the prediction decreases, with a maximum error of 9.54 %. This can be attributed to the incomplete development of smooth airflow, leading to locally nonuniform PM concentration in such conditions. In addition, the output from the AVL MSS-483 sensor is given in mg/m³. To calculate the time-dependent PM flow rate in mg/s, the following conversion needs to be performed (assuming a uniform distribution of PM within the cross-section of the exhaust pipe at the measuring point:

Output of PM concentration from the AVL MSS-483, and the converted PM flow rate under different operating conditions is presented in Fig.. It is important to note that as the engine speed decreases and torque increases, the inlet PM concentration of DPF gradually increases. On the one hand, the decrease in engine speed results in weakened gas flow and a deteriorated fuel–air mixture inside the cylinder. On the other hand, the increase in torque indicates an increase in the fuel injection quantity of the common rail system. The combined effect of these two factors significantly reduces the air–fuel ratio, resulting in a substantial deterioration in the hydrocarbon substances within the cylinder, leading to excessive PM emissions.

Fig. Clean DPF pressure drop under steady-state conditions: experimental vs. model.

Increasing the engine load has a positive impact on the rate of PM loading. However, it is important to note that the process of actual PM loading is lengthy. For instance, in this study, as the bulk volume of the DPF was 3.9 L, it would take more than 3.9 h to achieve every soot load of 1 g/L, even at a loading rate of 0.6 mg/s (maximum in the conducted tests) and a filtration efficiency of 100 %. Therefore, to reduce the simulation time, three operating conditions were chosen: a constant torque of 250 Nm and varying engine speeds of 1000 rpm, 1800 rpm, and 2400 rpm.

The variation of the saturation coefficient θ_{sat} is depicted in Fig.. It is indicated that deep-bed filtration dominated in the initial stage of the loading process. However, as the particles agglomerated and the soot bridges developed, cake filtration started to take place. This can be evidenced by the rapid increase in the saturation coefficient, which eventually converged to 1, indicating that the cake filtration efficiency reached its maximum. In addition, higher PM flow rate resulted in shorter convergence time. At the engine speeds of 1000 rpm and 1800 rpm, θ_{sat} reached saturation at 513 s and 4263 s, respectively. However, at an engine speed of 2400 rpm, where the PM flow rate was even less than half of that at 1000 r/min, θ_{sat} had not reached saturation within the entire simulated time of 18000 s.

The variation of the unit collector diameters of their corresponding wall slabs is shown in Fig. Combined with Fig., it can be observed that the trend of the variation of $dc,1$ (the unit collector diameter of the first layer) is consistent with the saturation coefficient. It is important to note that due to the collection of most of the incoming particles by the cake layer, the PM deposition decreased significantly from the 2nd layer to the 10th layer, resulting in slow growth of $dc,2 \sim dc,10$. In the simulation time of 18000 s, only at a speed of 1000 r/min, $dc,2 \sim dc,10$ reached saturation values around 8500 s, while under the other two operating conditions, they were still far from saturation. The distribution of wall porosity is shown in Fig. It is evident from the graph that the wall porosity was not uniform during the filtration process. The closer the area was to the interface between the cake layer and the wall, the faster the decrease in porosity. Except for the first layer, the variation of porosity in the other layers was relatively uniform. By comparing the graphs from Fig, it can be inferred that in deep-bed filtration, the interface between the wall and the cake layer near the inlet channel saturates first, while other areas of the wall gradually take effect in continuous filtration during the later stages. In addition, even when the cake filtration has fully developed, and there is a certain thickness of the cake layer present, deep-bed filtration can still proceed further. In similar situations, this modelling approach can achieve improved prediction accuracy. Furthermore, the lumped DPF model was validated by incorporating pressure drop prediction, and the results are shown in fig. At the operating points of 1000 rpm-500 Nm, 1600 r/min-500 Nm, and 2200 rpm-500 Nm, the average and maximum prediction errors of the model were 2.39 %, 3.17 %, 1.61 % and 4.45 %, 9.24 %, 3.76 %, respectively, reduced by 7.30 %, 2.79 %, 8.41 % and 12.24 %, 3.22 %, 16.24 %, respectively, compared with the original model.

Notably, the dynamic filtration model exhibited noticeably better prediction accuracy during both the transitional loading period (soot load < 0.6 g/L) and the later loading period (soot load > 2 g/L). This can be attributed to the consideration of two key factors in the model. Firstly, the gradual saturating process of the porosity-varying wall during the transitional stage was taken into account. Secondly, the continuous in-wall filtration after the complete formation of the cake layer was also considered. Otherwise, the pressure drop prediction results would be either higher and lower accordingly.

After analysing Fig., it is evident that while keeping the cell density fixed at 300 cpsi, the overall filtration efficiency of the DPF marginally improves with an increase in wall thickness, which is consistent with the findings of Tan et al. [26]., it can be found that altering the wall thickness predominantly influences the deep-bed filtration process, but has minimal impact on cake filtration. A larger wall thickness results in an increased particle deposition within the wall, leading to a notable improvement in deep-bed filtration efficiency. Nevertheless, this improvement makes only a tiny contribution to the total collected PM mass.

At the end of the simulation time of 18000 s, the impact of channel characteristics on pressure drop performance is illustrated in Fig. 12. An increase in cell density leads to a decrease in the effective filtering area and an increase in filtration velocity, resulting in an increase in pressure drop at both ends and along the channel. Under the same PM loading rate, a decrease in single-channel cake thickness leads to a significant reduction in the proportion of cake pressure drop. With an increase in cell density from 200 cpsi to 300 cpsi and 400 cpsi, the total pressure drop decreases by 14.9 % and 8.9 % respectively, while the cake pressure drop decreases by 52.0 % and 65.7 % respectively. It is important to note that the overall changes in total pressure drop and wall layer pressure drop are not significant due to the trade-off between filtration velocity and the amount of PM deposited in a single

channel. Additionally, the change in total pressure drop with cell density is not monotonic, as the total pressure drop at 300 cpsi is smaller than at 200 cpsi and 400 cpsi. This indicates that selecting an appropriate cell density can achieve optimal pressure drop characteristics and PM loading capacity.

Table 5

Case	σ /cpsi	ω_w /mm	L /mm	D /mm	$T_{DPF, in}/^{\circ}C$	Q_v /kg·h ⁻¹
1-3	200-300-400	0.19	140.7	257.7	345	1160
4-6	300	0.19-0.29-0.39	140.7	257.7	345	1160
7-9	300	0.19	140.5-190.5-230.5	257.7	345	1160
10-12	300	0.19	140.7	257.7-266.7-295.8	345	1160
13-15	300	0.19	140.7	257.7	165-240-345	1160
16-18	300	0.19	140.7	257.7	345	648-850-1350

On the other hand, an increase in wall thickness amplifies the effect of deep-bed filtration, resulting in a significant increase in wall layer pressure drop and subsequently, the total pressure drop. However, an increase in wall thickness has little impact on cake filtration. When the wall thickness increases from 0.18 mm to 0.28 mm and 0.38 mm, the total pressure drop increases by 39.8 % and 93.9 % respectively, while the cake pressure drop only increases by 4.2 % and 9.8 % respectively. This suggests that the DPF wall thickness should not be too large, as it would result in a significant pressure drop at the expense of minimal improvement in PM loading capacity. Therefore, precise manufacturing techniques of the honeycomb porous ceramic substrate are essential for the reliability of the aftertreatment, and even the engine system [59].

4.2.2. Influence of monolithic size on filtration performance

Fig. shows the influence of different DPF lengths (150.5–190.5–230.5 mm) and diameters (228.7–266.7–304.8 mm, i.e., 9–10.5–12 in.) on DPF filtration efficiency. From Fig. 13(a), it is evident that the overall DPF filtration efficiency slightly improves with increasing length. This improvement can be attributed to the lower flow velocity, which favors PM deposition. However, this increase in filtration efficiency is not significant under the same exhaust condition.

From Fig. It can be observed that widening the channels leads to an increase in wall filtration efficiency. However, the decrease in cake layer thickness results in a decrease in cake layer filtration efficiency and finally, there is a slight improvement in overall filtration efficiency. Hence, increasing the DPF filtering volume can enhance filtration, and compared to length, diameter has a greater influence on filtration efficiency.

The relationship between the size of the DPF and the pressure drop performance is illustrated in Fig.. When the diameter of the DPF remains constant and the length increases, the airflow path becomes longer, leading to an increase in flow velocity and a significant increase in pressure drop along the channel. However, even though the mass of a single cake layer in the channel remains unchanged at the same PM loading level, the thickness of the cake layer decreases, resulting in an increase in the effective filtration area and a decrease in filtration velocity. Consequently, both the pressure drop of the cake layer and the wall layer decrease as the length of the DPF increases from 150.5 mm to 190.5 mm and 230.5 mm. Specifically, the pressure drop of the cake layer decreases by 40.6 % and 55.0 % respectively, while the wall layer pressure drop decreases by 30.3 % and 42.1 % respectively. However, the total pressure drop only decreases by 5.2 % and 3.1 % respectively, which is resulted from the trade-off between the frictional and Darcy's pressure drop contribution.

On the other hand, when the length of the DPF remains constant and the diameter increases from 228.7 mm to 266.7 mm and 304.8 mm, the total pressure drop decreases by 39.5 % and 56.8 % respectively. The increase in channel width results in a decrease in cake layer thickness and gas flow velocity, leading to various components of the pressure drop decreasing to different extents. In conclusion, increasing the volume of the DPF helps to reduce pressure drop, and changing the diameter also has a more significant impact on pressure drop than changing the length. Therefore, it is recommended to increase the DPF diameter while sacrificing some length in order to achieve optimal filtration and pressure drop performance for a given DPF volume.

5.2.3. Influence of exhaust conditions on filtration performance Fig. 15 illustrates the impact of various inlet temperatures (ranging from 155 to 230 to 305°C) and exhaust mass flow rates (650 to 950 to 1250 kg/h) on the DPF filtration efficiency, observed that an increase in inlet temperature enhances the thermal motion of gas molecules, leading to a rise in exhaust volume flow rate and filtration velocity within the cake layer and wall layer, consequently causing a significant decrease in DPF filtration efficiency. In Fig. it can be inferred that higher exhaust mass flow rates also result in an increased exhaust volume flow rate, leading to reduced filtration efficiency. Additionally, it should be noted that different temperatures and exhaust mass flow rates are often indicative of diverse engine-out PM emissions. These discrepancies are evident according to Fig., which shows the relationship between pressure drop and collected soot mass over a simulation period of 18000 s. It can be observed that higher temperatures and lower flow rates correspond to higher DPF inlet PM concentrations. Therefore, this factor should be taken into consideration when comparing filtration efficiency. Fig. demonstrates that the deep-bed filtration curve exhibits one or two peaks. The first peak signifies the saturation of the first layer of the wall collector units at the cake-wall interface, exemplified by the circle in yellow. The second peak denotes the saturation of all the remaining wall unit layers, as exemplified by the circle in black. Once the wall deposition reaches its maximum capacity, the subsequent particles that enter the wall can only escape the DPF together with the exhaust gas, leading to a decrease in deep-bed filtration efficiency. It is evident that a higher PM loading rate can expedite wall saturation, allowing the overall efficiency to rapidly approach and surpass the cake layer filtration efficiency, as illustrated by the circle in green.

Fig. . The relationship between collected soot mass and pressure drop under different exhaust conditions.

The influence of DPF inlet temperature and exhaust mass flow rate on the pressure drop performance is shown in Fig. When the exhaust mass flow rate remains constant, increasing the DPF inlet temperature leads to an increase in exhaust volume flow rate and gas velocity, resulting in higher total pressure drop and individual component pressure drops. Among these components, the channel frictional pressure drop and wall layer pressure drop show a greater increase, contributing to a higher proportion of the total pressure drop. Specifically, increasing the DPF inlet temperature from 155°C to 230°C and 305°C results in a 43.4 % and 33.1 % increase in total pressure drop, respectively.

On the other hand, when the DPF inlet temperature remains constant, increasing the exhaust mass flow rate also leads to higher exhaust volume flow rate and gas velocity, resulting in increased pressure drops for each component. Decreasing the exhaust mass flow rate from 1250 kg/h to 950 kg/h and 650 kg/h leads to a 44.8 % and 71.9 % decrease in total pressure drop, respectively. Changes in temperature and exhaust mass flow rate primarily affect the exhaust volume flow rate passing through the DPF, which significantly impacts the total pressure drop of the DPF. In addition, small-scale fluctuations in engine operating conditions, particularly in the low load and low flow rate regions, do not significantly affect the proportions of individual component pressure drops. However, it is possible that instances of drastic engine condition variation, such as the active regeneration or drop to idle (DTI) event, could induce a cliff-shaped alteration in the gas temperature and volume flow rate within the DPF [60], making it more challenging to predict DPF performance. Therefore, properties of the solid- and gas-phase in DPF under these particular circumstances merit further research [61].

6. Conclusions

To accurately assess the deposition status inside the DPF and ensure efficient regeneration activities, this study proposes a lumped filtration- pressure drop model to describe the dynamic process of PM filtration. The influence of structural and operational parameters on both filtration and pressure drop characteristics were also investigated. The main findings of this study are as follows:

- (1). Compared to the original model, the average and maximum pressure drop prediction error of this model were reduced by up to 9.40 % and 17.25 %, respectively. The dynamic filtration model exhibited better prediction accuracy during the transitional period (soot loading < 0.6 g/L) and the later loading stage (soot loading > 2 g/L).
- (2). The increase in cell density results in a rise in the overall filtration efficiency of the DPF, while this improvement is tiny as the wall thickness increases. The comprehensive optimal performance of pressure drop and PM loading can be achieved by choosing suitable cell density. However, one should avoid excessive wall thickness, as it would result in a minor increase in PM loading capacity at the expense of a significant pressure drop.
As the length of the DPF increases, there is a slight improvement in overall filtration efficiency due to the decrease in gas velocity. As the diameter of the (3). DPF increases, the channel width increases, resulting in a decrease in filtration velocity and cake layer thickness, and an increase in wall filtration efficiency. On the whole, the overall filtration efficiency sees a slight improvement. Increasing the volume of the DPF is beneficial for improving filtration efficiency and reducing pressure drop, while the impact of changing the diameter is significantly greater than changing the length.
- (4). Elevated temperature and reduced flow rate resulting in increased PM concentration. Increasing the DPF inlet temperature and increasing the exhaust mass flow rate both cause a rise in the exhaust volume flow rate and filtration velocity, resulting in decreased filtration efficiency. In addition, pressure drop components, especially the frictional pressure drop and wall layer pressure drop, are increased. The influence of operating condition fluctuations in the low-flow-rate and light-load region on the percentage

contribution of pressure drop components is not significant. However, the estimation of DPF performance becomes complex in the cases of significant changes in gas temperature and volume flow rate within the DPF, for example, active regeneration and drop to idle process. Future investigation should be devoted to examining the DPFs' efficacy in these unique circumstances.

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